

Shaping and Reshaping of India through Indian English Literature

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Abstract:

India has been shaped and reshaped by various factors and Indian English Literature is the significant drive force behind it in the periods of before and after Independence as well as in the contemporary digital world. Indian English Literature drives India to mould shapes in the past and present through making various factors like creating intellectual images, proving various capabilities in English language, providing thought-provoking essentials, to the warns against misuse of power, by representing various state cultures, raising issues in the social and cultural conditions as well as providing strong personal, social and cultural presentations through films and documents. Moreover Indian English literature becomes the main source of education and also healing power of mind. The role of literature in this present Digital and AI conditions and future AI conditions is equally important.

Keywords: *Reshape, Literature, Society, Culture, Literary Capabilities, Construction, IEL (Indian English Literature) etc.*

Introduction:

India, the land of literature, arts, myths, scientific and technological progresses and trade capabilities, is the developed nation in the world throughout her various ages. Many havocs, movements, successes, facts, failures, driving forces in the history and in the present conditions shape and reshape India in the all possible domains. Indian English literature is the prominent drive force for the shaping of India throughout eighteenth and nineteenth centuries as well as through the pre-independence, post-independence and contemporary digital eras. Many writers with their thoughts, philosophies and articulations show directions to the India and the scenario changes through the ages. While thinking about present and future of India it becomes essential to have glimpse on past to acknowledge the whole picture of shaping and reshaping.

Past Scenario:

Different literary major landscapes of Indian English literature can be measured for having look on past of India. According to the records and sources of information, Indian English literature during eighteenth century was in the forms of memoires and sketches, however not in the documented forms. During nineteenth century, first novel *Rajmohan's wife* (1864) by Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay, Lal Behari's *Govinda Samanta* (1874) as early fiction, in 1878 *Bianca or The Young Spanish Maiden* by first woman novelist Toru Dutt were written with contemporary issues. Initialisation in the history of Indian English Literature was the starting point of creating writers and their images in English. However, during early decades of twentieth century, various capabilities have developed among Indian English writers in English language. Very famous trio in IEL: R. K. Narayan, Mulk Raj Anand and Raja Rao shaped

India through their portrayals of rural and poor class India in their fictions. Poems of Rabindranath Tagore and Sarojini Naidu enhanced poetic landscape of that time. Nissim Ezekiel, Anita Desai, Ruskin Bond, Khushwant Singh, Kamala Das, Nirad Choudhari, Bhabani Bhattachary, Manohar Malgaonkar, Kamala Markendaya, Dilip Chitre, these all poets and fiction writers from various states, with different mothertongues had provided thought provoking essentials through their literary works in English language.

Globalisation, through the nineteen ninety's decade and around the time, reinterpreted post-colonialism which can be called as decoding of colonialism. Salman Rushdie, Amitav Ghosh, Vikram Seth, Rohinton Mistry and Arundhati Roy are the offsprings of this era who have represented various social and historical issues with their new dimensions. Presentations of decentralization of subjects by these writers can be inculcate in the literary shaping and reshaping of India.

Present Realities:

After solving the world famous cliché of Y2K at the entering of this century, software in computers and technology has developed rapidly throughout the nations of world and India is the prominent nation in that development. That dynamic enhancement effects on each and every possible domains of human being's social and also personal life all over the world. Obviously Indian English literature is not exception of that scenario. Till date, twenty six years of this century skilfully determined changes in the IEL with innovative contents and direction showing thoughts. Writers like Arvind Adiga, Kiran Desai, Jhumpa Lahiri, Chetan Bhagat, Amish Tripathi, Anand Neelkantan, Kavita Kane, Dirjoy Datta, Kiran Nagarkar, Ashwin Sanghi, Preeti Shenoy, Anita Nair Meena Kadasamy and many more

have explored on various elements of today's human being's complicated life. They speak on human experiences, social norms, educational truths, cultural colours, absurd relations among human beings, mythical references, reinventions of mythical figures, domestic and sexual violence, women's identity, crisis of marginalised people, business ethics, ecological issues, psychological assumptions etc.

Through their writings contemporary writers contribute in the shaping of nation with the various factors. From very personal life of every citizen to the image of nation on world platform, IEL builds the architect on different elements like,

1) Socio-political awareness: Generation of youth in this present time awakens themselves on both social and cultural levels. Youths come in the framework with their own ideas and are doing energetic, useful and innovative deeds for society. They start to express themselves in oration and in the writing forms as they have strong technological platform for example different social media, they present their thoughts in their own ways. Most of them are writing on the contemporary burning socio-political issues and their writings come under the umbrella term 'literature' according to the new norms of literature. As the youths are form different states, the language of communication is none but 'English'. So the literature plays significant role behind this crucial awareness. The awareness is essential for the sake of nation and this consciousness turns nation into gaining determined solutions.

2) Social reforms: By considering socio-political awareness, youth as well as various groups of people take initiatives in social reforms. Writers are out of them who are participating in the movements of social reforms. However before that, they had written about social reforms through their writings and show the directions to

others. It is the fact that need of social reforms was in existence from pre-independence era however according to the changing and complex scenario of society nowadays, new and hard questions arise day by day in Indian society and it becomes need of time to solve the questions within that time. Movements for social reform is the way to demolish the crisis and literature proves itself as the backbone behind solving issues, as it explores situation of women and marginalised groups. With this, writers and youths cultivated enough cultural confidence among them and that is important in aligning the map of developed India. Moreover, ILE provides content on social issues to films right from R. K. Nayan's *Guide* (1958) to Chetan Bhagat's campus novels of present era.

3) Creating National identity: Identity is the unique thing that any person, place or abstract thing have as its own reflection. Nation has their own identity on the world platform and India becomes successful in creating her own image in the chaotic plethora of the world through Indian English literature. Writers and their texts spread message of Indian contexts to the world, as a result India creates her identity as the nation of educated and philosophical people and it breaks the past image of India.

4) Global Representations: As English is the prominent language of communication in World, Indian English literature represents India globally. Many writers in IEL are writing on different Indian contextual references through their literally works. This global representation explores not only the flexible nature of Indian society but also the capabilities of Indians, specifically the capacities and skills of literary writings by Indian and recent example of this is the celebrated writing by Banu Mushtaq. Besides this fact, Indian writings in English shows depth of knowledge that Indian people have in different domains of talent. So this global representations

are important factors in shaping India as the capable India on the world platform.

5) Digital Age: Besides above conditions, the present age is the age of digitalization and most recurrent issue of AI. After Covid Pandemic use of screen and online things are increased in almost fields in India. This is the transition period of India from 'non-technology time' to 'everything digital' age. This crucial point will be considered as 'turning point' in Indian history. Nowadays we have face as well as we have to seek happiness in using online tools as we get readymade things and also readymade torture by using online apps. In the field of literature, the use of online or digital becomes regular in practice with both possibilities: happiness of acceptance of writing and fear of rejection. Because of online source writers, in India with English language, can communicate within few seconds with readers and get responses immediately. This 'less time' becomes the cause of pleasure and grief. Nowadays certain quantity of people are busy in writings and readings various fictional and non-fictional writings on different online apps, for example, Pratilipi, the app of stories written and read by Indians within thirteen state languages including English language. This fact in present condition is the unavoidable situation that is moulding India into new diagram. The future has with its lot of possibilities and crucial points with evolution and development of AI.

Role of Literature for Future:

Indian English writers have much scope in the future to share innovative thoughts and shape of mentality of people. However in the form of AI, literature has certain pros and cons. Most crucial issue is of 'creativity' as it is the 'soul' of literature however AI creates literature on its own and there is the threats of copying it by many people. AI provides readymade things as it is supposed to replaces human brain as a result it

is the most risky thing in the field literature. Literature, on the one hand, is the pure form of creativity after thinking and rethinking by its creator, by writer the living being himself or herself. AI the machine, on the other hand, is always ready to create literary matter within a moment with its revised forms. So the role of literature in shaping and reshaping of India becomes more responsible because literature is the important factor for development of any nation, responsibility of writers increases in the crucial and new situations. AI is and will create short story, novel, poem and non-fiction writings however we cannot call AI as writer. In this very developed techno-age writers keep their ways in creating literary situations and thoughts as any machine cannot imitate human sensations and emotions exactly. Alive literature will have to face dry AI and surely literature will keep itself alive and dynamic with same past glory.

Conclusion:

Past teaches us certain things which we memorise in present and configurate for future. India is the nation with glorious past, magnificent present and undecidable future. After shaping and reshaping by various factors, India becomes and becoming concrete nation which has its own separate image in the world. Literature, especially Indian English Literature is the important factor in the process of creating India as confirm nation as growth of literature is the growth of nation. Throughout the years IEL contributes India in the development of thought process. Surely literature will play lucid role in future also.

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